

Length of Stay as Correlate of Satisfaction with Nursing Care Among Orthopaedic Patients in Two Selected Teaching Hospitals in Osun State

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Abstract:

Prolonged length of stay (LOS) has many disadvantages for both hospitals and patients, including the satisfaction to nursing care received. This study explored the link between length of stay and satisfaction with nursing care among orthopaedic patients in two selected hospitals (OAUTHC and LAUTECH) in Osun State, Nigeria. It also identified the average length of stay of orthopaedic patients and determined patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for the study comprised all patients scheduled for elective and emergency, Orthopaedics surgeries in OAUTHC and LAUTECH during the study period. Adapted Structured questionnaire were used to obtain information about the length of stay of surgical patients and their level of satisfaction with nursing care at the health facilities. The validity of the instrument was determined using face and content validity. The results showed that the average length of stay of patients at the two hospitals (OAUTHC and LAUTECH) in Osun State is 24 days and that the largest percentage (65.5%) of the patients at the two hospitals had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing care. Furthermore, the

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results also revealed that there is no significance relationship between the length of stay of patients and their level of satisfaction with nursing care (chi-square value $\chi^2 = 55.86$, $df = 62$ $p > 0.05$) at the two hospitals in Osun State. The study therefore concluded that there is no link between the length of stay and the level of patient satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals in Osun State.

Keywords: Length of Stay, Patient Satisfaction, Nursing Care, Orthopaedic Patients,

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Introduction

Orthopaedic patients are very much eager to be admitted at the initial stage of their care. Later, the patients get aggressive when the health workers keep on prescribing/writing needed materials in successions. Nurses' interventions had helped to counsel the patients who see reasons to comply with the care they receive. The provision of quality health services is a crucial competitive advantage of health service providers (Alsaqri, 2016; Reck, 2013). Patient satisfaction has become an established outcome indicator of the quality and the efficiency of health care systems (Al-Abri & Al-Balushi, 2014; Riley, Gordan, Hudak, & Rindal, 2014). Surgical services represent approximately 30% of all hospital expenses (Haider, Obirieze, & Velopulos, 2015). It is generally accepted that a significant burden of disease requiring surgical intervention exists globally with 234 million operations performed each year (Weiser & Lipsitz, 2015).

Length of stay (LOS) is calculated as the total number of nights spent in hospitals by in-patients divided by the total number of discharges. LOS of in-patients in hospitals is computed by first calculating the number of hospitals days (or bed-days or in patients days) from the date of admission. LOS continues to remain one of the most popular indices used in assessing hospital performance and efficiency. LOS can also be defined as the period from the day of admission to the day of discharge or death (Bleustein, Rothschild, & Valen, 2014). Shorter LOS has been correlated with a significantly higher risk of readmission in multiple studies and countries (Eapen, Reed, Yanhong, Kociol, Armstrong, Starling, & Hernandez, 2013), the results of El Camino Hospital's improvement efforts demonstrate that these risks can be mitigated as hospitals seek the optimal LOS for maximizing quality and minimizing cost.

Unnecessarily prolonged stays in hospital may be dangerous for patients. Patients with prolonged LOS are also at higher risks of nosocomial infections and unplanned readmissions (Schneider, Hyder, Wolfgang, Hirose, Choti, Makary, 2012; Jannasch, Kelch, Adolf, Tammer, Lodes, Weiss, et al; 2015). This however prolonged LOS disadvantages for both hospitals and patients (Freitas, Silva-Costa, Lopes, Garcia-Lema, Teixeira-Pinto, Brazdil & Costa-Pereira, 2012). Borghans, Kleefstra and Kool (2012) reported correlation between length of stay and patient's satisfaction only in the department of pulmonology in a study conducted over a period of eight years.

The study therefore investigated length of stay as correlate of satisfaction with nursing care among orthopaedic patients in two selected teaching hospitals in Osun State. The study specifically examined:

- i. the average length of stay of Orthopaedic patients at the two hospitals;
- ii. the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals; and
- iii. relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care at the two hospitals

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions:

1. What is the average length of stay of Orthopaedic patients at the two hospitals in Osun State?

2. What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals in Osun State?

Research Hypothesis

This hypothesis was generated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care at the two hospitals in Osun State.

Methodology

Descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted by the researcher. The target population included all patients between the ages of 18 and 70 years and those patients who were able to comprehend and could communicate in Yoruba or English in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo during the study period. The total admission of orthopaedic patients who had surgeries in the last three months at OAUTHC, Ile-Ife and LAUTECH, Osogbo were 70 and 24 patients respectively. Total enumeration technique (census) was used for patients booked for elective and emergency orthopaedic surgeries in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo.

The instrument for data collection was questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into 3 Sections A to C. Section A focuses on respondents socio-demographic characteristics. Section B will assess the length of hospital stay of Orthopaedic patients in the two hospitals using structured questions. Section C determined patient's level of satisfaction with orthopaedic care in the two hospitals. The validity of the instrument was determined using face and content validity. The instrument was subjected to intensive screening by the experts in the field of nursing education and Tests & Measurement. The experts appraised the items on the basis of ambiguity, relevance and sentence structure. A trial test was conducted to determine the reliability of the scale. The test was administered to a sample of 15 patients at University College Hospital, (UCH), Ibadan other than the sample of the study. The reliability coefficient was estimated using the Cronbach's Alpha formula. The obtained Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was 0.91 which is considered reliable for the purpose of this study.

After permission has been given by the appropriate authority to administer questionnaire to the study participants in OAUTHC and LAUTECH, questionnaire was self-administered by the researcher to the patients in the orthopaedic wards. Specific clarifications on the elements of the questionnaire were also given to the respondents by the researcher. The copies of the questionnaire filled were collected and checked for completeness at the point of collection. Data analysis used relevant descriptive and inferential statistics (percentage distribution and frequency, means, standard deviation and chi-square statistic). The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the average length of stay of Orthopaedic patients at the two hospitals in Osun State?

To identify the average length of stay of patients at the two hospitals in Osun State, the mean of length of stay of the patients was computed in days.

Table 1: The average length of stay of patients at the two hospitals in Osun State

Days	N (%)	\bar{X}	SD
2-30	44 (75.9%)	24.2	27.4
31-90	12 (20.7%)		
91-150	2 (3.4%)		
Total	58 (100%)		

Table 1 showed that majority (75.9%) of the respondent stayed in the hospital admission between 2– 30 days, few (20.7%) of them stayed in the hospital admission between 30-90 days, while minority (3.9%) of them stayed in the hospital between 91-150 days. The results from Table 1 also showed that the average length of stay of patients at the two hospitals in Osun State is 24 days.

Research Question 2: What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals in Osun State?

To determine the patients' level of satisfaction with nursing care, patients' level of satisfaction with nursing care, the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores of the instrument were computed and categorized into three as low, moderate and high level respectively. The minimum and maximum scores were 50 and 99 with a mean and standard deviation of 75.07 and 10.63 respectively.

To compute the norms, the following method was used

Mean = 75.07

SD = 10.63

Min = 50

Max = 99

$\bar{X} - SD = 75.07 - 10.63 = 64.44$

$\bar{X} + SD = 75.07 + 10.63 = 85.70$

Range

Scores from 50 – 64: Low Level

65 – 86: Moderate Level

87 – 99: High Level

Table 2: Patients' level of satisfaction with nursing care at the two hospitals?

Level	Frequenc		\bar{X}	SD
	y	Percent		
Low	10	17.2	2	0.59
Moderate	38	65.5		
High	10	17.2		
Total	58	100.0		

The results from Table 2 showed that the largest percentage (65.5%) of the patients had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing at the two hospitals.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care at the two hospitals in Osun State.

To test this hypothesis, responses of the patients in the two hospitals to items in Sections B and C of the questionnaire were computed. The relationship between the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care and the length of stay in the hospital was examined using Chi-square statistical analysis.

Table 3: The Chi-square Statistics of the relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals

	χ^2	df	Sig.	P
Length of stay in the hospital Levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care	55.86	62	0.695	> 0.05

Table 3 showed a chi-square value $\chi^2 = 55.86$, $df = 62$ $p > 0.05$ (The P value which is 0.695 is greater than 0.05). This indicates that there is no significant relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care at the two hospitals in Osun State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

The first finding is that the average length of stay of patients at the two hospitals in Osun State is 24 days. This was quite lower than the description of prolonged hospital stay of 90 days described by Banaszak-Holl, Liang, Quinones, Cigolle, Lee and Verbrugge in their study in 2014. This quite lower average length of stay of patients is beneficial to both hospitals and patients (Freitas, et al., 2012): increasing access to treatment, reduced nosocomial infections, reduce bed-occupancy rate per patient (Banaszak-Holl, Liang, Quinones, Cigolle, Lee, & Verbrugge, 2014).

Secondly, it is discovered that the largest percentage (65.5%) of the patients had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing at the two hospitals. A report of study from DuPree, Anderson and Nash (2014) however, warned on the exclusive use of patients' satisfaction as the indicator of quality health care service. This is because some patients may verbalize true positives and false positives. Other quality indicators like timely access to care, safety and affordability of service must be involved.

Thirdly, it is also discovered that there is no significant relationship between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The result showed the evidence of moderate quality service to the majority of surgical orthopaedic patients in the two settings under study. Patients satisfaction level is an indicator for evaluating quality of health service (Kingdon & Newman, 2013; Mishra & Gupta, 2012). A report of study from DuPree, Anderson and Nash (2014) however, warned on the exclusive use of patients' satisfaction as the indicator of quality health care service. This is because some patients may verbalize true positives and

false positives. Other quality indicators like timely access to care, safety and affordability of service must be involved.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that there is no link between the length of stay and the levels of patients' satisfaction with nursing care in the two hospitals. Findings showed that nursing care has no significant relationship with the length of stay in the hospitals because there are many other compounding factors that affect the length of stay in the hospitals such as financial constraints on the part of patient, inappropriate patient's diagnosis and their pain threshold, lack of adequate water supply and provision of oxygen in the theatre, lack of constant electricity supply etc. if all these factors can be properly improved upon with adequate nursing care then the length of stay of patients in the hospital can be improved.

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